

relationship between skeletal pattern occlusion and TMD

Proposal

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ALIREZA MOZAHAB

With help of Professor 元坤

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-Necessary Performance:

One of the common and annoying problems in the head and face area is temporomandibular disorders or TMD. TMD It is a general term and refers to clinical problems that involve the masticatory muscles, the temporomandibular joint, and both. the most common manifestations are the sounds of the temporomandibular joint , the limitation of jaw movements and stiffness of the masticatory muscles. The prevalence of TMD in different societies is estimated between 12 and 20% and it's up to 65% including subclinical symptoms. The common age is also reported between 20 and 40 years old. Regarding the etiology of temporomandibular disorders till now , two hypotheses of occlusal disharmony and psychological pressure have been proposed, but none of them have not been supported and confirmed by scientific sources. Therefore, this research aims to investigate the relationship between facial skeletal pattern and temporomandibular joint disorder in a review of published articles that published in last 10 years.

- Expressing :

the problem of temporomandibular disorders (TMD) is a branch of medical and dental problems related to pain and disorder of the function of masticatory muscles and temporomandibular joints. Signs and symptoms of TMD include regional pain in the face and front of the ear, joint noises and movement problems and limitation of jaw movement (1).

This disorder, after pain in the tooth is the most common complaints of patients in the dental clinic. According to various researches, the percentage of people suffering from temporomandibular disorders in society is 50-60% and most of the time it affects patients between the second and fourth decade of life. On average, women are 2 times more at risk than men. For its correct diagnosis and classification, the set of signs and symptoms must be organized in an objective and standard way.(1,2).

In previous researches , there are several criteria for evaluating TMD. In 1992, Dworkin and LeResche, presented the research diagnostic criteria or RDC/TMD for temporomandibular disorders, which was a reliable and valid system for standardizing and improving the methodological quality of clinical researches in TMD (3).

However, it was a complex tool that required training to operate. Therefore, it is sometimes necessary to use simpler questionnaires to screen patients. For this purpose, in 1994, the Fonseca Anamnestic Index (FAI) was proposed, which evaluated the severity of TMD based on its signs and symptoms (4).

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The questionnaire is standardized and the validity and reliability of the questionnaire in other languages have been examined in previous researches (5).

It consists of 10 questions that classify the patient into four categories according to symptom severity: (a) no TMD, (b) mild TMD, (c) moderate TMD, and (d) severe TMD. Also, its use is recommended for screening TMD patients in public health and screening services due to its simplicity, quick application and low cost (6).

Early diagnosis and treatment of Temporomandibular disease is very important because these disorders are progressive in nature and become more extensive with time (7).

Temporomandibular disorders are a problem with different causes and are related to mental stress, occlusal interference, improper position or loss of teeth, masticatory muscle dysfunction, external and internal changes in the structure of the temporomandibular joint, the relationship between disc and condyle or a combination of These factors(8).

Angle classification is accepted today as an excellent and simple method for the general interpretation of malocclusion and basically describes the anteroposterior relationships of first molars and permanent canines and is divided into four categories. Normal occlusion where the teeth are on the occlusion line and the mesiobuccal cusp of the upper first molars are placed in the mesiobuccal groove of the lower first molars. Class I malocclusion, in which the relationship of the first molars is normal in terms of the mesiodistal position, but the occlusion line is disturbed due to the displacement and rotation of the teeth. In Class II malocclusion, the lower first molars have a more distal position than the upper first molars, and there is a certain disharmony in the anterior area and facial lines, but the occlusion line has no specific characteristics and has two subgroups. Class II/ Div 1 malocclusion is characterized by a narrow maxillary arch, protruding incisors, abnormal lip function, and Class II/ Div 2 malocclusion is characterized by a narrow maxillary arch, crowding of the maxillary incisors along with their lingual inclination. Class III malocclusion where the upper first molars are placed in a more mesial position and the occlusion line does not have a special feature (9).

Perhaps one of the most important and controversial factors in the occurrence of temporomandibular disorders is occlusal trauma. There are many researches with conflicting results in this field. Improper occlusal positions can increase muscle activity and ultimately increase the possibility of tissue damage. In 1998, Seligman et al. examined two groups of dental and oral hygiene students in America for the presence of pain or dysfunction during chewing with the help of questions and clinical examinations and examination of diagnostic casts and stated that although occlusal disorders, There

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are no important predisposing factors for muscle tenderness, but in people with Deep Bite, wide muscle tenderness is more common than in people with less vertical overlap, and in a person with class II occlusion, tenderness is increased when touching the TM joint (10).

In a research conducted in 2018, it was stated that the role of occlusal conditions is weaker than psychological factors, and therapists should focus on factors such as stress, anxiety, and depression to treat TMD patients (11).

Therefore, due to the many contradictions that have been presented in the results of different researches, this research will be conducted in order to reach a general result regarding the effect of factors of different occlusal conditions on the occurrence of TMD.

- Previous researches

Al-hadad et al in their research in 2022 investigated the three-dimensional positional and morphological evaluation of the temporomandibular joint in skeletal class II patients with mandibular retrognathism in different vertical skeletal patterns. They retrospectively reviewed the CBCT images of 80 adult patients. Class II subjects with normal sagittal position of the upper jaw and retrognathism of the lower jaw were divided into three groups of 20 people based on the angle of the lower jaw and the ratio of the height of the face. A significant difference was observed in the hyperdivergent and hypodivergent groups compared to the normal group in the vertical and anteroposterior position of the mandibular cavity, the vertical condyle slope, and the width and length of the condyle. The hyperdivergent group showed significantly the highest inclination of the condyle with the midsagittal plane. They concluded that condylar-fossa position and morphology differed with different vertical facial patterns in individuals with skeletal class II mandibular retrognathism. These differences can be considered during TMD diagnosis and orthodontic treatment (12).

Chuan Fan et al in their research in 2021 investigated the bone morphology of the temporomandibular joint of class I and class II malocclusion in a normal skeletal model: a cone beam computed tomography research. CBCT images of bilateral TMJ in 67 individuals with skeletal class I and moderate mandibular angle (26 men and 41 women, age range 20-49 years) were evaluated in this research. Subjects were divided into class I and class II according to molar relationship and retroclination of maxillary incisors. TMJ angular and linear measurements were evaluated. They stated that intragroup comparisons showed statistical differences for articular prominence tendency, glenoid fossa width, glenoid fossa width ratio to glenoid fossa depth, condylar angle and

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intercondylar angle between malocclusion groups. Measuring the shape of the glenoid cavity did not show a significant difference between the left and right sides. Females showed greater differences in TMJ morphological parameters between the three malocclusion groups than males (13).

In their 2017 research, Cordray et al investigated the relationship between occlusion and TMD and stated that 3D analysis of dental arch displacement (DAD) and condylar displacement (CD) from SCP/CR to MIC/CO using position Temporomandibular joint and instrumentation indicate the position of the condyle, but a clear correlation between occlusion and TMD is clearly lacking. But in most of the studied studies, the relationship between occlusal conditions and TMD has been mentioned. Also, displacement of the condyle is more common in people with temporomandibular joint problems than other people, and displacement of the dental arch and displacement of the condyle are also related to TMD. Mandibular condyle displacement caused by dental arch displacement causes common muscle contraction headache (CMCH) and temporomandibular dysfunction (TMD) (14).

In 2015, Park et al., in their research , compared the position and morphology of the condyle based on three-dimensional cone beam computed tomography based on the vertical skeletal pattern. Orthodontics of Halim University Hospital were examined. Subjects were divided into three equal groups based on the mandibular plane angle: low divergent, norm and divergent groups. The morphology of the condyle and mandibular cavity and the position of the condyle were compared between the groups. They concluded that the position and morphology of the condyle in TMD patients is significantly different from that of healthy individuals (15).

In their 2013 research , Almăsan et al investigated the skeletal pattern in people with temporomandibular joint disorders using sixty-four people with malocclusion, over 18 years old. Temporomandibular disorders were evaluated clinically based on Holkimo anamnestic index. Subjects were subjected to lateral cephalogram. Subjects were grouped into class I, II and III based on the sagittal skeletal pattern (ANB angle). 24 patients with TMD and 40 patients without TMD were divided into two groups. The significant difference between the interincisal angle was higher in class I and II. Overjet was higher in people with TMD. The midline shift was significantly greater in the TMD group, and in class III subjects, the SNB angle was greater in the experimental group (16).

In their 2013 research, Arieta-Miranda et al investigated the spatial analysis of condyle position based on the sagittal skeletal relationship, assessed by cone beam computed tomography. This was a retrospective research of previously acquired CBCT images of

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45 subjects. People were divided into three equal groups including class I (normal face pattern) and class II and III (long face pattern). They concluded that the upper distance of the condyle to the glenoid fossa was smaller in class II and class III compared to class I group. The anterior distance of the condyle to the articular eminence showed a significant difference when comparing class I with class II and class III groups. No statistically significant difference was observed in the posterior condyle distance between the groups. The ridge angle was different between the three groups, while the length of the ridge showed a significant difference comparing class I with class III group (17).

In their 2012 research, Barrera-Mora et al investigated the relationship between malocclusion, benign joint hypermobility syndrome, condyle status and TMD symptoms. 162 people were analyzed using the Rocabado temporomandibular pain analysis. Holkimo index parameters; Modified Carter-Wilkinson test. It was used to record the position of the condyle (MPI). and stated that there was a significant relationship between skeletal pattern, transverse malocclusion, right and left posterior synovial pain, hypermobility scale, gender and malocclusion pattern in patients with TMD was significantly higher than healthy people (18).

-Research Method:

This research reviews the results obtained from the existing articles on the relationship between facial skeletal pattern and temporomandibular joint disorder. In this way, the articles available in Pubmed, web of science, ISI, scopus, Google scholar with similar topics in the 10-year period from 2012 to 2022 are selected and reviewed based on the entry and exit criteria, and the articles are received from It will be done by searching the keywords mentioned in Table 1.

Table 1. Target keywords

CIII	CII	occlusion	TMD	skeletal pattern
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After searching the articles and reading the title and abstract, the articles are translated. In this research, based on the investigated variables, Table No. 2 will be completed. After reviewing the articles and the obtained results, the results will be interpreted and the results obtained in the research will be compared.

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Table 2.

Row	the writer	year of publication	Conclusion

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria

Studies in English

Clinical studies and case reports and prospective

Articles in the period from 2011 to 2022

Articles with full text

Exit criteria

Studies that are not indexed in the above scientific databases

Articles whose full text is not available.

Animal studies

Meta-analysis studies

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-Resources:

1. List T, Jensen RH. Temporomandibular disorders: Old ideas and new concepts. *Cephalalgia*. 2017;37(7):692-704
2. M, Grossi P, Grossi M. Gender differences in temporomandibular disorders in adult populational studies: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of oral rehabilitation*. 2018;45(9):720-9
3. M. Research diagnostic criteria for temporomandibular disorders: review, criteria, examinations and specifications, critique. *J craniomandibDisord J*. 1992;(4)6:255-301
4. Freitas ,ALd G, Valle Bonfante ,DMD Fonseca RGO (Porto Alegre). *J craniomandibular disfunção da anamnese pela Diagnóstico .SFTd*. 1994:23-8
5. F. Anxiety and temporomandibular joint disorders among law students in Iran. *Journal Radiology, Pathology and Surgery*. 2018; 7(4):28-33. <http://dx.doi.org/10.32598/3dj.7.4.145>
6. J. Reliability of a questionnaire for diagnosing the severity of temporomandibular disorder. *Brazilian Journal of Physical Therapy*. 2009;13:38-43
7. A.BARONE,L.SBORDONE,L.RAMAGLIA.Craniomandibular disorders and orthodontic treatment need in children.*J oral Rehabil*.1997:2-7
8. Motghare V, Kumar J, Kamate S, Kushwaha S, Anand R, Gupta N, Gupta B, Singh I. Association Between Harmful Oral Habits and Sign and Symptoms of Temporomandibular Joint Disorders Among Adolescents. *J Clin Diagn Res*. 2015 Aug;9(8):ZC45-8. doi: 10.7860/JCDR/2015/12133.6338. Epub 2015 Aug 1. PMID: 26436046; PMCID: PMC4576640.
9. Thilander B, Pena L, Infante C, Parada SS, de Mayorga C. Prevalence of malocclusion and orthodontic treatment need in children and adolescents in Bogota, Colombia. An epidemiological study related to different stages of dental development. *European journal of orthodontics*. 2001;23(2):153-68
10. Seligman DA, Pullinger AG, Solberg WK. The prevalence of dental attrition and its association with factors of age, gender, occlusion, and TMJ symptomatology. *Journal of dental research*. 1988 Oct;67(10):1323-33.
11. Manfredini D, Lombardo L, Siciliani G. Temporomandibular disorders and dental occlusion. A systematic review of association studies: end of an era?. *Journal of oral rehabilitation*. 2017 Nov;44(11):908-23.

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12. Al-Hadad SA, ALyafrose ES, Abdulqader AA, Al-Gumaei WS, Al-Mohana RA, Ren L. Comprehensive three-dimensional positional and morphological assessment of the temporomandibular joint in skeletal Class II patients with mandibular retrognathism in different vertical skeletal patterns. BMC oral health. 2022 Dec;22(1):1-2.
Fan XC, Ma LS, Chen L, Singh D, Rausch-Fan X, Huang XF. Temporomandibular joint osseous morphology of class I and class II malocclusions in the normal skeletal pattern: a cone-beam computed tomography study. Diagnostics. 2021 Mar 18;11(3):541 .13
- Cordray FE. The relationship between occlusion and TMD. Open Journal of Stomatology. 2017;7(01):35 .14
- Park IY, Kim JH, Park YH. Three-dimensional cone-beam computed tomography based comparison of condylar position and morphology according to the vertical .journal of orthodontics. 2015 Mar 1;45(2):66-73 korean skeletal pattern. The G. Skeletal Băciuț ,M Iancu ,HA, Bran S, Lascu L Almășan ,M Băciuț ,OC Almășan .16
pattern in subjects with temporomandibular joint disorders. Archives of Medical Science. 2013 Feb 21;9(1):118-26 .15
17. Arieta-Miranda JM, Silva-Valencia M, Flores-Mir C, Paredes-Sampen NA, Arriola-Guillen LE. Spatial analysis of condyle position according to sagittal skeletal relationship, assessed by cone beam computed tomography. Progress in orthodontics. 2013 Dec;14(1):1-9.
C.A., Carrera, J.M.L., Ballesteros, ,Labruzzo ,.E.E ,Escalona ,.Barrera-Mora, J.M .18
E.J.C., Reina, E.S. and Rocabado, M., 2012. The relationship between malocclusion, benign joint hypermobility syndrome, condylar position and TMD symptoms. CRANIO®, 30(2), pp.121-130